

Studies on Complexation of Some Thiopicolinamides with Niobium(V)

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Complexation reaction between Nb^V and thiopicolinmethylamide and thiopicolinanilide has been studied in dry DMF-methanol medium. These compounds have coordination number nine, are insoluble in common organic solvents and do not show any sharp melting point. IR spectra of the complexes suggest coordination through sulphur and nitrogen atom of the pyridine ring. Elemental analysis indicates metal to ligand ratio as 1 : 3. The compounds are diamagnetic in nature. A possible dimeric structure is proposed for the complexes.

MANY metal complexes of thiopicolinamides are reported in literature¹. Due to tautomerism these ligands have high coordinating tendency. Interest in the chemistry of niobium has increased during the last forty years as it is used in aerospace projects, reactor technology, electronics *etc.* Since there is little information about chelation or analytical behaviour of niobium with sulphur-containing ligands and its compounds with thiopicolinamides are not reported, it was considered worthwhile to investigate the complexation of niobium(V) with thiopicolinmethylamide and thiopicolinanilide.

Experimental

Double-distilled DMF, dry methanol, niobium pentachloride (Fluka) and pure grade B.D.H. chemicals were used without further purification. IR spectra (4000-200 cm^{-1}) were recorded in nujol mull. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made by Gouy method.

Preparation of ligands : Thiopicolinmethylamide (m.p. 77°) and thiopicolinanilide (m.p. 51°) were prepared by reported methods^{2,3}. The purity of the compounds was ascertained from their melting point, IR spectra and elemental analyses.

Preparation of complexes : Solution of niobium pentachloride in dry DMF-methanol mixture was

refluxed separately with thiopicolinmethylamide (TPMA), and thiopicolinanilide (TPA) under anhydrous conditions for about 2 and 4 h, respectively. A yellow precipitate obtained in both the cases was digested for ~2 h, then filtered and washed with dry DMF-methanol mixture. The complexes obtained were insoluble in common organic solvents and sensitive to moisture. They did not show any sharp m.p. but decomposed above 190° and 217°, respectively. Analysis of the complexes is given in Table 1. Molecular weight of these complexes could not be determined due to their insolubility in common organic solvents.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured at 306 K by Gouy method using $Hg[Co(CNS)_4]$ as a standard. Measurements were corrected only for diamagnetic correction and not for temperature-independent paramagnetism.

μ_{eff} for the Nb-TPMA and Nb-TPA complexes was found to be 0.44 and 0.31 B.M., respectively at 306 K.

Results and Discussion

The bands between 3300 and 3040 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the ligands, assigned to ν_{NH} , are not present in the spectra of the complexes.

TABLE I

Compound	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					
	Nb	C	H	N	S	Cl
Nb-(TPMA)	15.20 (15.08)	40.17 (40.84)	3.47 (3.40)	13.00 (13.61)	15.11 (15.56)	11.67 (11.51)
Nb-(TPA)	11.67 (11.63)	53.98 (54.00)	3.06 (3.00)	10.41 (10.50)	11.82 (12.00)	8.97 (8.88)

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Presence of the SH group indicated in the spectra of the ligands between $2705-2660\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is not observed in the spectra of the complexes suggesting that coordination takes place through the SH group. A strong peak at 950 cm^{-1} in TPMA spectra and peaks at 955 cm^{-1} and 925 cm^{-1} in TPA spectra may be due to ν_{SH} and are absent in the spectra of the complexes supporting the view that coordination takes place through the SH group.

Absorption due to C=N stretching vibrations becomes stronger and is shifted to lower region in the spectra of both the complexes indicating further that complexation had taken place.

In the high frequency region (above 650 cm^{-1}) pyridine vibrations show very little shift upon complex formation⁷. However, those at 604 cm^{-1} in TPMA spectra and 645 cm^{-1} in TPA spectra (in-plane ring deformation), and 430 and 400 cm^{-1} in TPMA spectra, and 405 cm^{-1} in TPA spectra (out-of-plane ring deformation) are shifted to higher frequency upon coordination to metal. Such shift has been observed in the case of several metal complexes⁸.

The bands at $570-530$ and $390-365\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the Nb-TPMA spectra and $365-345\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the Nb-TPA spectra may be due to $\nu_{\text{Nb-S}}$ and are nearly similar to those indicated for $\nu_{\text{Nb-S}}$ by other workers⁶.

Peaks at 340 cm^{-1} in the Nb-TPMA and at 320 cm^{-1} in the Nb-TPA spectra are also nearly similar to that indicated by other workers for $\nu_{\text{Nb-Cl}}$ terminal bond⁴.

In general, bridging metal-halogen stretching frequencies are lower than terminal metal-halogen stretching frequencies and bands observed between 290 and 240 cm^{-1} in the spectra of both the complexes may be due to metal-chlorine (bridging) stretching vibrations⁶. This assumption is supported by such difference in the stretching frequencies of

terminal and bridging metal-halogen bonds observed in the case of several metal complexes⁹.

Magnetic measurements indicate the compounds to be diamagnetic having d^0 electronic configuration. The low value of μ_{eff} may be due to temperature-independent paramagnetism and orbital contribution.

On the basis of above results the following dimeric structure is suggested for the complexes.

Where

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